

LINGUOCULTURAL LACUNES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THEM

Tursunova Dilnoza Alisherovna

*1st year doctoral student of the Karshi State University, comparative literary
studies, cross-linguistics and translation studies
Karshi, Republic of Uzbekistan*

Abstract: The article gives an explanation of the term "lacune". This article presented a classification of linguocultural lacunes. The term "lacuna" is used in linguistics and methodology teaching a foreign language as a tool for describing difficulties perception of text in a non-native language.

Key words: language lacune, literary text, verbal and non-verbal images, false associations, grammatical categories.

Understanding a text in a non-native language is determined by the degree of proficiency the reader's understanding of this language, as well as the stock of cultural knowledge. Insufficient command of the language and lack of necessary knowledge information about the subject of description can interfere with adequate perception artistic text.

Difficulties in the perception of a literary text by a foreign cultural carrier can be described using the term "lacuna". Usage the term "lacuna" as a tool for describing the difficulties with which faced by speakers of a different language and culture in the process of perception of a literary text, makes it possible to systematize these difficulties, to develop a classification of lacune.

The purpose of this article is to describe and systematize the different types of lacunes obtained in the course of an experimental study of perception Russian literary texts by Chinese and Uzbek students. This study was carried out using the method questioning of Chinese and Uzbek students, as well as translation from Russian into Uzbek.

In this article, lacunes are understood as deviations from adequate interpretation of the Russian literary text by foreign cultural reader. The proposed classification of lacunae is based on the model perception of the text, providing for the distinction between two types of image call - verbal and non-verbal - and, accordingly, two levels perception of the text - linguistic and non-linguistic, or figurative-conceptual. Inadequate correlation of verbal images with each other leads to the formation of gaps at the language level, and inadequate correlation verbal and "objective" images - to the emergence of figurative-understanding silent lacune.

A phonetic lacune occurs with inadequate perception of sound new form of the text due to the mismatch of phonological systems the language of the reader, and the language in which the text is written. For example, an intern China took the combination "young master" (Pushkin A. S. "Young lady-peasant woman") as a "young guy". Identification of sound complexes [bar'in] - [par'n '] due to the fact that in Chinese noisy consonants do not differ in voicelessness/voiceness.

Thus, inadequate reception of the specified passage of text when listening, it is determined by the mismatch of systems of consonant phonemes Russian and Chinese languages. Lexical gaps are subdivided into proper lexical and lexico-semantic. Proper lexical lacunae include the following types of lacune:

1) the sound complex is perceived as a word, but does not correlate with the definition in a fixed subject way (this word stands out in the analyzed text as incomprehensible). How incomprehensible Uzbek students distinguish the text contains mostly words that are part of the passive vocabulary Russian language, as well as ethnographic words;

2) the sound complex is not perceived as a word (the student does not know this language unit);

3) the sound complex is erroneously perceived as another word.

The sound complex is interpreted as another word according to the following reasons:

- a) mixing of lexical homonyms, paronyms, homographs;
- b) false associations (phonetic, semantic-word-formation body, etc.).

The reason for mixing homonyms, as a rule, is unequal lexical homonyms in terms of their use, namely: the word of the perceived text can be limited in use and little is known (or not known), while the homonymous word is in common use. For example, colloquial small ("used is used to designate a person (male) - a carrier of any qualities) ([2:223]) in the passage Her father was a good fellow // In the past belated century ... (Pushkin A. S. "Onegin") mistakenly realized as a homonym small ("insignificant in size, size"; "insignificant in strength, degree of manifestation", etc. (see: [2:222–223]), related to neutral vocabulary and included in the active vocabulary students. The expression *good fellow* was interpreted by the Uzbek students as "a kind but inconspicuous person", "having a small rank", "having a low level of development", "a man of small stature", "not very kind", "not very rich".

Compare also the interpretation of the word light (Here is my Onegin on freedom ... and finally saw the light; Other, strict worries // And in the noise of light and in silence // The dream of my soul is disturbed - Pushkin A. S. "Eugene Onegin") as "life", "world", "society of that time", "day", "happiness", "freedom", "teaching". Students name the values twice personal homonyms: light - "electromagnetic radiation, perceived eye-catching"; "lighting", "light source", etc. and light - "peace", "surrounding people, society", "the upper layer of the privileged classes of the bourgeois-noble society" (see: [3:44-45]).

The interpretation of words unfamiliar to a foreign student can be based on false associations, among which are:

- a) phonetic associations;
- b) phonetic-semantic associations, in particular - the influence of words native language, similar in sound and similar in meaning;
- c) semantic-word-building associations.

As an example of false prediction, let us analyze the waters into Uzbek expressions Low house with blue shutters (Yesenin S. A. "Low house with blue shutters"). During the experiment several translations were received: "With blue glass low house", "Low house with a blue support"; "With a blue door low house. In our case, it is difficult to adequately translate the word shutters, which denotes a reality unknown to Uzbek students and has no equivalent tape in the form of a word in the Uzbek language (the Russian-Uzbek dictionary conveys the equivalent of this word by a paraphrase, which can be literally translated as "window doors" or "window doors"). Interpretation of this words are carried out on the basis of the meaning predicted by the context. The latter "suggests" Uzbek students a certain circle of words, serving to name "parts of a building, a structure for housing." In addition, the epithet blue [shutters] determines the selection of equivalents "window" / "glass" (compare the usual combination of blue windows). Translation the word shutters as "pillar" / "support" is due to the fact that the meaning of this the word is motivated by its internal form; noun (compare "to put") is correlated by Uzbek students with the subject (part of the structure), which is placed vertically.

The presence of an epithet in some cases makes it possible to adequately predict the meaning of a word incomprehensible to the Uzbek student. Yes, meaning the words "howl" (You are sweet to me, dear howl - Yesenin S. A. "Low house with blue shutters") Uzbek students define through the semantics adjective darling, explaining this dialectics. Colloquial darling howl was translated as "motherland", "native land", "mother nature". This interpretation is close to adequate, since the word howl ("share", plot, allotment in the ground, meadows") in the context Yesenin's poem is used in the meaning of "native land".

The word bread, used in the meanings of "food product, baked from flour" and "grain from which flour is prepared, going to baking such a product", does not form the plural form (see: [3:601]). However, bread as "cereals (rye, wheat)" is used mainly in the plural form - bread.

This polysemantic word of the Russian language corresponds to different Uzbek lexemes. So, bread ("baked product") is equivalent to Uzbek-"non", and the shape of bread corresponds to the word "don ekinlari."

Uzbek students mistakenly correlate the forms of bread (only on essential number) and bread as singular and plural forms numbers are similar to table-table pairs, which leads to inadequate interpretation of the word bread and at the lexical-semantic sublevel: students identify the forms of bread ("food product") and bread ("bread mark") according to the concepts they define. However, this gap should be called morphological, since the indicated identification is carried out on the basis of the connection of the considered forms into one grammatical pair.

The characteristic of this subtype completes the analysis of linguistic lacunes.

REFERENCES:

1. Арутюнова Н. Д. Язык и мир человека / Н. Д. Арутюнова. – М., 1999. – 304 с.
2. Словарь русского языка : в 4-х т. / РАН, Ин-т лингвистич. исследований ; под ред. А. П. Евгеньевой. – 4-е изд., стер. – М., 1999. –Т. 2. : К–О. – 736 с.
3. Словарь русского языка : в 4-х т. / РАН, Ин-т лингвистич. исследований ; под ред. А. П. Евгеньевой. – 4-е изд., стер. – М., 1999. –Т. 4. : С–Я. – 797 с.
4. Чистякова А. Б. Практическое пособие по методике преподавания русского языка как иностранного / А. П. Чистякова. – Х., 2007. – 127 с.
5. Tursunova, D. A. Q., & To'Rayeva, S. E. Q. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF ROLE PLAY IN TEACHING PROCESS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(6), 232-236.
6. Shermatovna, M. O., Qizi, X. S. T., & Qizi, A. S. R. (2022). LEXICAL-SEMANTIC FIELDS OF ENGLISH BORROWINGS. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(2), 126-130.

7. Tursunova, D. A. Q. (2022). THEORITICAL BASES OF LEXICOLOGY. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 189-197.
8. Tursunova, D. A. Q., & To'Rayeva, S. E. Q. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF ROLE PLAY IN TEACHING PROCESS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(6), 232-236.